

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN IMPLICIT BIAS AND HEALTH DISPARITIES AMONG HEALTHCARE USERS IN DUTSIN-MA, KATSINA STATE

BY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17627292>

Abstract

Implicit bias refers to unconscious attitudes or stereotypes that individuals, including healthcare providers, may hold without conscious awareness. These biases can significantly influence decision-making and interpersonal interactions in healthcare, contributing to disparities in access, quality, and outcomes. In communities such as Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria, where healthcare users differ in socioeconomic status, gender, age, and education, implicit bias may lead to unequal healthcare experiences and results. This study find out the relationship between implicit bias and health disparities among healthcare users in Dutsin-Ma. The population of this study comprised all individuals aged 18 years and above who accessed healthcare services in Dutsin-Ma within the past 12 months. A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was adopted, and 100 participants were selected through convenience sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation at a 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed that socioeconomic status, language, and education level significantly influenced perceived quality and timeliness of healthcare services and this results in health disparities. There was a statistically significant relationship between implicit bias and health disparities ($r = 0.432$, $p < 0.05$). These results highlight the need for equity-focused healthcare training, inclusive communication, and bias-reduction interventions to improve patient outcomes and trust in healthcare systems.

KEYWORDS: Implicit Bias, Health Disparities, Socioeconomic Status, Language, Healthcare Access, Dutsin-Ma, Katsina Stat

Introduction

Healthcare systems worldwide are intended to deliver quality, fair, and equitable care to all individuals, regardless of their social, cultural, or demographic backgrounds. However, in practice, disparities in access, treatment, and outcomes persist, especially among marginalized and underserved populations. These disparities often result in some patients receiving lower-quality care, longer wait times, or less attention from healthcare providers, depending on their socioeconomic status, education level, language, or social identity (Braveman et al., 2011).

A major factor contributing to these inequalities is implicit bias, also called unconscious bias. Implicit bias refers to automatic attitudes,

beliefs, or stereotypes that individuals hold without conscious awareness (FitzGerald & Hurst, 2017). Unlike deliberate prejudice, implicit bias occurs involuntarily and can conflict with a person's stated intentions or values. In healthcare, these biases can subtly influence decisions and behaviors, affecting how clinicians communicate with patients, interpret symptoms, or decide on treatment plans. For example, a healthcare provider may unconsciously assume that a patient from a low-income background is less likely to follow medical advice, leading to less detailed explanations or fewer preventive recommendations (Hall et al., 2015).

Health disparities are systematic differences in health outcomes or healthcare delivery between population groups, often resulting from unequal access to services or discriminatory practices. These disparities can manifest as differences in disease prevalence, treatment quality, or patient satisfaction, particularly among socially or economically disadvantaged groups (Davido et al., 2008). For instance, patients from poorer communities may experience longer waiting times, less attention from healthcare workers, or lower-quality interactions, which can negatively affect health outcomes and trust in healthcare systems (Braveman et al., 2011).

In Nigeria, patient satisfaction is a crucial indicator of healthcare quality. Yet, few studies have investigated how implicit bias affects patient experiences, especially in semi-urban community like Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. Dutsin-Ma is a socially and economically diverse area, where healthcare users vary in income, education, language, and social status. This diversity creates conditions in which unconscious biases among healthcare providers can influence who receives timely care, the quality of communication, and the perceived attentiveness of healthcare workers. Healthcare users in Dutsin-Ma access services from public hospitals, private clinics, pharmacies, and traditional health centers, making it important to understand how biases may operate across different types of facilities.

Given these realities, this study investigates the relationship between implicit bias and health disparities among healthcare users in Dutsin-Ma. By examining how unconscious provider biases shape patient experiences, the study aims to identify groups most affected, highlight patterns of disparity, and provide actionable recommendations to improve equity and fairness in local healthcare delivery. Understanding these dynamics is essential for designing interventions

that ensure all patients, regardless of social or economic background, receive respectful, timely, and effective care.

Statement of the Problem

Healthcare systems are expected to provide fair, equal, and patient-centered services to all individuals, regardless of their background, social class, or gender. However, implicit bias, which is the unconscious stereotypes or assumptions held by healthcare providers, continues to shape clinical interactions and healthcare decisions globally. These biases, though often unintentional, can lead to unequal treatment, poor communication, and differing health outcomes for certain groups.

In a diverse and growing community like Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, healthcare users include people from various social classes, ages, genders, and ethnic identities. Despite diversity, there is limited research on how implicit bias may lead to difference in healthcare access, quality, and outcomes in the area. Some individuals may unknowingly experience longer wait times, less attention, or less empathetic communication due to provider assumptions about their background or worthiness.

This creates a serious problem because it reinforces existing health disparities and undermines trust in the healthcare system. If left unaddressed, implicit bias can lead to dissatisfaction, mistrust, non-compliance with treatment, and even avoidable complications. Therefore, this study sought to investigate how implicit bias may lead to health disparities among healthcare users in Dutsin-Ma and recommend actionable solutions.

Literature Review

Concept of Implicit Bias

Implicit bias refers to the unconscious attitudes, stereotypes, or associations that individuals hold toward specific social groups, often without conscious awareness (Staats et.al., 2015). These

biases can subtly influence perceptions, judgments, and behavior, even when one consciously endorses non-prejudiced views. In healthcare, implicit bias is particularly concerning because providers often make rapid decisions under pressure. Research shows that many healthcare professionals exhibit levels of implicit bias similar to the general population (Maina et. al., 2018).

In healthcare settings, implicit bias can manifest as differential treatment, lesser empathy or communication, and assumptions about patient adherence or behavior based on social group membership. These unconscious biases may influence diagnosis, pain management, referrals, or follow-up care without overt intent (Vela et. al., 2022).

Concept of Health Disparities

Health disparities refer to systematic and preventable differences in health outcomes, access to care, quality of care, or disease burden among different population groups (e.g., by race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, gender). These disparities often stem from structural, social, and provider-level factors (Gulamali et al., 2025)

Disparities manifest in many ways: unequal rates of disease (e.g., hypertension, diabetes), differential mortality, lower access to preventive services, and poorer patient satisfaction. Structural factors such as resource allocation, health infrastructure, insurance or payment systems, and geographic distribution play a central role (Wilson, 2022).

Health disparities can also be seen as the systematic differences in the health status and treatment of population groups that result from unequal access to healthcare resources and discriminatory practices. These disparities disproportionately affect vulnerable populations based on socioeconomic status, ethnicity, language, education, gender, and geographic location (Ghosh-Choudhary et. al., 2021). In

countries like Nigeria, structural challenges in healthcare delivery intersect with provider-level factors such as implicit bias, further widening the gap in access and quality of care.

Relationship between Implicit Bias and Health Disparities in Healthcare

Many studies document that implicit racial/ethnic bias among healthcare providers correlates with disparities in communication, diagnosis, treatment decisions, adherence, and outcomes. A systematic review by Hall et al. (2015) found that providers tend to have implicit pro-White and negative implicit attitudes toward racial/ethnic minorities, influencing their clinical interactions and contributing to unequal care.

Socioeconomic status remains one of the strongest predictors of differential healthcare treatment in Nigeria. Burgess et. al., (2020) noted that patients perceived as wealthy or influential often received quicker and more respectful attention in public hospitals. This finding was echoed by Joseph et al. (2021), who argued that even well-intentioned providers might make skewed assumptions based on a patient's class or appearance, leading to inequality in care. Education level also plays a role in how seriously patients' complaints are taken, with less educated individuals sometimes dismissed or overlooked (Vela et. al., 2022).

In addition, gender and age-based implicit biases have been reported in clinical practice. Female patients, for instance, are sometimes undertreated for pain (Blair et. al., 2011). Older adults may be denied certain treatments based on ageist assumptions. While this was less prominent in the Dutsin-Ma study, these dimensions are important to consider in broader discussions of bias and disparity.

Language and communication also play a central role in perpetuating disparities. Patients who cannot speak the dominant local language often experience neglect or longer waiting times

(Gopal et. al., 2021). This aligns with findings from the current study in Dutsin-Ma, where over half of respondents believed language differences affected how quickly they received care. The social perception of patients, including their appearance, clothing, and accent, was also a factor in biased treatment. Additionally, Blair et. et. al., (2011) argue that implicit bias is a hidden driver of health disparities and propose a research and intervention agenda for counteracting these biases in healthcare.

Interventions and Mitigation Strategies

Efforts to address implicit bias in healthcare have focused on training, awareness, and structural reforms. Joseph et al. (2021) suggested that bias-reduction strategies should include perspective-taking, emotional regulation, and counter-stereotyping. In Nigeria, community-based interventions, staff diversity, and policy enforcement may offer more practical solutions (Hatfield, et. al., 2020). Healthcare institutions should adopt protocols that ensure equitable treatment regardless of language, appearance, or social background.

In summary, existing literature supports the idea that implicit bias significantly contributes to health disparities. This evidence underscores the need for ongoing research, policy changes, and practical interventions in both urban and rural Nigerian communities.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to find out the relationship between implicit bias and health disparities among healthcare users in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State.

Research Question

The following research question was raised to guide the study:

Is there a relationship between implicit bias and health disparities among healthcare users in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between implicit bias and health disparities among healthcare users in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey design. The population of the study comprised all individuals aged 18 years and above who accessed healthcare services in Dutsin-Ma within the past 12 months, 100 participants were selected through convenience sampling and Data was collected within the community by visiting households, public gathering spots and places of worship where diverse groups of healthcare users can be reached. Trained research assistants explained the purpose of the study, obtain informed consent, and administer the questionnaires through face-to-face interviews for respondents with limited literacy and self-administered forms for literate respondents. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, and percentages) was used to summarize the characteristics and experiences of the respondents. Inferential statistics, specifically Pearson correlation was used to test the hypothesis and determine the relationship between implicit bias and reported healthcare disparities. The level of statistical significance will be set at 0.05.

The Result of the Study

Answer to Research Question

Table 1. Is there a relationship between implicit bias and health disparities among healthcare users in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State?

S/N	ITEMS	TRUE	FALSE	TOTAL
1.	I have denied or delayed treatment because of my appearance, clothing, or accent.	68 (68 %)	32 (32 %)	100 (100%)
2.	Health workers seem to prioritize patient who appear wealthy or influential.	70 (70 %)	30 (30%)	100 (100%)
3.	Speaking the local language influence how quickly I am attended to in health facility	55 (55 %)	45 (45 %)	100 (100%)
4.	My ethnic background affects the way health workers treat me	28(28 %)	72 (72 %)	100 (100%)
5.	I have avoided visiting a health facility due to fear of unfair treatment.	21 (21 %)	79 (79 %)	100 (100%)
6.	Patients from certain tribes or religion received faster care.	53 (53 %)	47 (47 %)	100 (100%)
7.	Health workers sometimes ignore or overlook my concerns compared to other patients.	61 (61 %)	39 (39 %)	100 (100%)
8.	Health workers are more friendly and respectful towards certain groups of patients.	55 (55 %)	45 (45 %)	100 (100%)
9.	My level of education affects how seriously my complaints are taken	51 (51 %)	49 (49 %)	100 (100%)
10.	I feel I would have better access to healthcare if I belong to a different social group.	50(50 %)	50 (50 %)	100 (100%)

Interpretation

Table 1 indicate that a strong relationship between implicit bias and health disparities among health care users in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The highest reported factor was preferential treatment toward wealthy or influential patients (70%), followed by

appearance (68%). The language difference was also reported to influence the speed of service (55%), and education level affecting seriousness of care (51%). These patterns suggest that socioeconomic and linguistic factors are major drivers of health disparities in the area.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 2: Relationship between implicit bias and reported healthcare disparities among health care users

Variables		Implicit Bias	Health Disparities
Implicit Bias	Pearson Correlation	1	.432
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Health Disparities	Pearson Correlation	.432	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

(Significant (P<0.05))

Interpretation

Table 2 reveals an r-value of 0.432, P-value of 0.000 in the line of the significant 2-tailed, and the alpha value = 0.05, hence the alpha value is greater than the P-value. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between implicit bias and health disparities among healthcare users in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State is rejected. This means there is a statistically significant relationship between implicit bias and health disparities among healthcare users in the study area.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study indicate that there is a strong relationship between implicit bias and healthcare disparities in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The highest proportion of respondents (70%) reported that health workers seem to prioritize patients who appear wealthy or influential. Similarly, 68% indicated that appearance, clothing, or accent could lead to denial or delay of treatment. More than half (55%) agreed that speaking the local language influences how quickly they are attended to, while 51% believed that education level affects how seriously their complaints are taken. These results suggest that socioeconomic status, linguistic ability, and educational attainment are key areas where implicit bias manifests in the local healthcare system.

These findings are consistent with those of FitzGerald and Hurst (2017), who found that unconscious attitudes toward patients' socioeconomic and educational status influence healthcare professionals' clinical decisions, leading to differential treatment. Similarly, Hall et al. (2015) demonstrated that language differences and cultural assumptions are often associated with poorer communication and reduced patient satisfaction. Gulamali et al. (2025), also observed that wealthier patients in public hospitals tended to receive faster and

more personalized care compared to those perceived as poor, confirming the role of perceived social status in healthcare disparities. The current findings also align with Blair et al., (2011), who reported that implicit biases related to ethnicity, gender, and class lead to unequal healthcare delivery. The pattern in Dutsin-Ma suggests that while ethnicity was less frequently reported (28%) compared to socioeconomic and linguistic factors, it still contributes to disparities for certain groups. This is similar to Hall et al., (2015) who observed that ethnicity played a lesser role than economic class in shaping patient experience in semi-urban Nigerian communities. Overall, the results highlight the importance of addressing implicit bias in the community healthcare context. Training programs that raise awareness of unconscious biases, promoting language-inclusive communication, and ensuring equal treatment regardless of economic appearance or education are critical. This will not only improve equity in care delivery but also strengthen trust between healthcare providers and community members.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Healthcare workers in Dutsin-Ma and other healthcare settings should undergo regular workshops on understanding, recognizing and reducing unconscious biases, particularly those related to socioeconomic status, language, and education.
2. Hospitals and clinics should recruit or train multilingual staff to ensure patients who do not speak the dominant local language receive the same level of attention and care.
3. Health facilities should implement standardized treatment protocols that reduce the possibility of preferential

treatment based on appearance, wealth, or influence.

4. Community Sensitization: Public awareness campaigns should educate community members about their rights to equitable healthcare and encourage reporting of discriminatory practices.
5. Local health authorities should monitor and enforce anti-discrimination policies, ensuring that all patients are treated with fairness and dignity.

Conclusion

This study has shown that implicit bias plays a significant role in shaping healthcare experiences and outcomes in Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. Socioeconomic status, language proficiency, and educational level emerged as major determinants of how patients perceived their treatment in health facilities. The statistically significant relationship between implicit bias and health disparities underscores the urgent need for targeted interventions to ensure fairness in healthcare delivery. Addressing these issues through bias-awareness training, language inclusivity, and strict adherence to equitable service protocols can help bridge the gap in healthcare quality and strengthen trust between healthcare providers and the community. By confronting unconscious bias, the healthcare system in Dutsin-Ma can move closer to achieving equity, inclusiveness, and improved patient satisfaction.

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